

High-Throughput Hybridization Assay as First-Line Diagnostic Test for Sarcomas

Clinical Assessment in a Tertiary Referral Center

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• **Context.**—Sarcomas are rare and highly heterogeneous mesenchymal tumors with deceptive morphologic features that pose a challenge for precise diagnostics. Chromosomal rearrangements generating pathognomonic gene fusions are useful diagnostic markers, traditionally tested using singleplex standard of care assays with limited diagnostic yield. NanoString nCounter technology has emerged as a robust solution with multiplexing capabilities.

Objective.—To optimize NanoString effective coverage of specific entities and conduct a validation study to support its clinical implementation.

Design.—We reconfigured a NanoString codeset by including a set of probes for detecting gene fusion variants of solitary fibrous tumors, low-grade fibromyxoid sarcomas/

sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcomas, and undifferentiated small round cell sarcomas, totaling 188 probes. A technical validation study was conducted with 96 retrospective samples. Additionally, 76 prospective samples were evaluated to assess the assay's clinical performance.

Results.—Both technical and clinical validation studies showed that NanoString's codeset reached >88% sensitivity and 100% specificity, compared with standard of care methods, and superior diagnostic yield as a first-line test. Our design enabled the detection of almost all fusion variants of NGFI-A binding protein 2 (*NAB2*) with signal transducer and activator of transcription 6 (*STAT6*) in solitary fibrous tumors, as well as cAMP responsive element binding protein 3 like 1/2 (*CREB3L1/2*) rearrangements in all low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma/sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma cases. Identification of specific gene fusions of undifferentiated small round cell sarcoma was also improved, but additional strategies are necessary to attain full coverage.

Conclusions.—The NanoString platform demonstrated good sensitivity, specificity, and superior diagnostic yield. It is a cost-effective assay with rapid turnaround time, low sample consumption, streamlined analysis, and easy customization. Therefore, it is a promising alternative first-line diagnostic tool for routine sarcoma testing.

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Sarcomas constitute a highly heterogeneous and complex group of mesenchymal malignancies. They encompass more than 100 distinct morphologic entities and represent less than 1% of all malignant neoplasms in adults, though this proportion increases in pediatric cancer.¹ This wide spectrum of rare neoplasms varies regarding aggressiveness, clinical presentation, histology, and genetics. Still, overlapping histomorphology and immunophenotype add complexity to the diagnostic workup.¹ Nevertheless, precise diagnosis is imperative, as certain subtypes need specific treatment approaches or tailored follow-up, or they can influence patient eligibility for clinical trials.^{2–5}

While traditional methods for differential diagnosis of sarcomas relied on morphology and clinical presentation, genetic markers have become essential for precise diagnosis. From a genomic standpoint, sarcomas can be broadly classified into 2 categories: those characterized by a simple karyotype, and a second group with complex karyotypes,

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exhibiting no specific genomic patterns.^{1,6,7} The first group is characterized by recurrent chromosomal translocations or intrachromosomal inversions, generating gene fusions (GFs). These GFs are typically confined to specific entities. They are recognized as the main driver oncogenes of the disease, thereby serving as ideal diagnostic biomarkers,⁸ whose identification is often mandatory for differential diagnosis.^{2,4,9,10} However, certain fusion partners, such as EWS RNA binding protein 1 (*EWSR1*), are highly promiscuous and can be involved in several GF-defined distinct entities. In addition, DNA breakpoints can occur at different genomic locations between the same partner genes, giving rise to exonic variants and hence introducing another layer of complexity.^{11–13} Standard of care methods for GF detection, namely reverse transcription–polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) and fluorescence in situ hybridization (FISH), suffer from limited resolution and multiplexing capabilities that hinder their utility as the vast repertoire of GFs in sarcomas continues to grow.

Consequently, alternative molecular diagnostic modalities are gaining traction for the accurate classification of these neoplasms, such as targeted RNA-sequencing (RNA-seq) or DNA methylation profiling.^{14–16} Although these techniques, tailored for formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissues, enable the simultaneous detection of multiple fusion transcripts, or classify the samples in a single run, they are burdened by high costs, long turnaround time, as well as the need for complex bioinformatics. NanoString technology is a customizable and multiplexed platform that utilizes color-coded tags, eliminating the need for reverse transcription or amplification steps, thereby allowing for the direct measurement of messenger RNA levels. Several recent publications have highlighted the successful use of NanoString technology in detecting specific GF transcripts in sarcomas^{17–21} and other GF-driven tumors.^{22–24} However, there is a need for clinical validation studies that support the eventual implementation of the technology in the diagnostic setting. Moreover, optimization of the effective coverage of the assay would also enhance its adoption.

In this study, we conducted a technical validation and a clinical evaluation in a referral tertiary center of a customized NanoString panel with improved coverage for detecting GFs in a wide variety of bone and soft tissue tumors. We devised a comprehensive codeset design with imbalance and GF junction specific probes for GF of NGFI-A binding protein 2 with signal transducer and activator of transcription 6 (*NAB2::STAT6*) in solitary fibrous tumors (SFTs), which present a high variety of breakpoints. We also included imbalance probes targeting cAMP responsive element binding protein 3 like 1/2 (*CREB3L1/2*) for low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma (LGFMS) and sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma (SEF) identification, and extended the coverage for GFs in undifferentiated small round cell sarcomas (USRCS).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Case Selection

Tumor specimens were processed routinely and assessed at our hospital, a reference center for bone and soft tissue tumors. For the technical validation study, we selected retrospectively 96 cases from 2014 to 2023 that had undergone molecular testing assessing pathognomonic GFs with targeted RNA-seq as previously described.¹² FISH was also performed in 46 out of 96 samples. For evaluation of clinical performance, 76 prospective cases were assessed with NanoString in parallel with FISH and/or targeted RNA-seq assays in the diagnostic

workup. The tumors were reviewed by experienced soft tissue pathologists (G.C., D.M., and E.d.A.), who evaluated the histopathologic features, immunohistochemistry, and FISH. These cases were analyzed in batches of 12 cases per run in the NanoString platform. More details on case selection are described in Supplemental Figure 1 (see supplemental digital content at <https://meridian.allenpress.com/aplm> in the June 2025 table of contents, containing 3 figures and 6 tables).

This study was performed following the standard Spanish ethical regulations, and it was approved by the Institutional Review Board CCEIBA (Comité Coordinador de Ética de la Investigación Biomédica de Andalucía, code 2253-N-20/1236-N-20). Clinical analyses were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

RNA Isolation and Quantification

Total nucleic acid was extracted from FFPE tissue samples using the Agencourt Formapure Kit (A33341; Beckman Coulter, Indianapolis, Indiana) following the manufacturer's instructions. Input material was 10- μ m sections of FFPE blocks with >70% of viable tumor area. The isolated RNA was quantified using a Qubit RNA HS assay kit in combination with a Qubit 4 fluorimeter (Q32852; Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts).

NanoString Probe Set Design

We reconfigured the sequence-specific probe set described by Chang et al¹⁷ that targets the RNA sequences across the junction site of 174 GF variants in 25 sarcoma types. In a first version of the codeset, we introduced 3 probes targeting GF variants of *CIC::DUX4* (*CIC*, capicua transcriptional repressor; *DUX4*, double homeobox 4 gene) and a probe for detecting *BCL6* corepressor (*BCOR*) internal tandem duplication (*BCOR* ITD). Additionally, a set of probes targeting different exons of the genes signal transducer and activator of transcription 6 (*STAT6*), cAMP responsive element binding protein 3 L1 (*CREB3L1*), and cAMP responsive element binding protein 3 L2 (*CREB3L2*) were added in order to detect expression imbalance of the 3' and 5' exons involved in the GFs *NAB2::STAT6* and *NAB2::STAT6* and *FUS/EWSR1/PAX5::CREB3L1/2* (*NAB2*, NGFI-A binding protein 2; *FUS*, FUS RNA binding protein; *EWSR1*, EWS RNA binding protein 1; *PAX5*, paired box 5). These GFs are the molecular hallmarks of SFT and LGFMS/SEF, respectively, which were not covered in the original codeset due to the high variability of the breakpoint sequences involving many different exons. An expression imbalance approach allows minimization of the number of probes but does not render information about the fusion partner. Four probes were designed to specifically bind to each gene's 5' and 3' regions, respectively (*CREB3L1*, *CREB3L2*, and *STAT6*) (Supplemental Figure 2). Oligonucleotide probes were designed in collaboration with NanoString Bioinformatics (NanoString Technologies). As the number of tags is limited to 192 in a single codeset, we removed the 18 probes targeting the GFs of inflammatory myofibroblastic tumors, which we can detect using a targeted RNA-seq assay in our clinical setting. This initial version of the panel includes a total of 188 probes, consisting of 24 imbalance probes, 160 junction probes, and 4 housekeeping probes. Since some fluorescence barcodes were still available, we added 4 junction probes for the most common exonic variants of *NAB2::STAT6* fusions in a second version of the codeset (192 probes: 24 imbalance probes, 164 junction probes, and 4 housekeeping probes). These junction probes target the exonic variants 4-2, 6-16, 5-16, and 6-17 which represent the more frequent ones in our experience.²⁵

The retrospective cohort included 60 cases tested with the first version of the codeset and 36 additional cases analyzed with the second. The prospective cohort was only tested with the second version of the codeset.

RNA/Probe Hybridization

High-performance liquid chromatography purified oligonucleotide probes (Integrated DNA Technologies, San Diego, California) were dissolved at 5 nM (probes A), 25 nM (probes B), or 10 nM (protector probes, probes P) in Tris–ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid buffer (10 mM Tris pH 8, 1 mM EDTA) to create the master

stock pool of probes and stored at -80°C in aliquots to minimize freeze-thaw cycles. Before each assay, an aliquot of each master stock probe pool was further diluted $8.25\times$ in nuclease-free water to generate the working stock of each probe pool. Thus, each probe A will be present at 0.6 nM, each probe B will be present at 3 nM, and each probe P will be present at 1.2 nM. Finally, the hybridization master mix codeset was assembled by mixing the Gene Fusion TagSet Reagent (Barcoded Reporter and Capture Probes, NanoString Technologies) with the working stock of each probe pool (A, B, and P) according to the manufacturer's protocol. The final concentrations of each probe in the hybridization mixture were 20 pM (probes A), 100 pM (probes B), and 40 pM (probes P). A total of 250 ng of RNA (with the exception of cases where there was insufficient RNA) was hybridized to the tagged probe set for 19 hours at 67°C , followed by incubation at 4°C for up to 1 hour. The hybridized RNA/probe mixture was processed in the NanoString Prep Station (NanoString Technologies) using the high-sensitivity setting. Therefore, automatically, the excess codeset was washed away, and the hybridized codeset/RNA complexes were purified and immobilized onto the nCounter cartridge system. Finally, the cartridge was sealed and transferred to a NanoString Digital Analyzer device (NanoString Technologies) for data collection. The nCounter cartridge was scanned at 555 fields of view to identify the unique fluorescent signatures (barcode) associated with each probe.

Data Analysis

Raw counts of the optical barcodes for each sample were subject to technical normalization using the internal positive spike-in controls with nSolver software version 4.0 (NanoString Technologies). The normalized count values were exported to Excel 2016 software (Microsoft, Redmond, Washington). The extreme statistical outlier method was used to detect the presence of an expressed fusion using junction probes. A fusion transcript was designated as "expressed" if the normalized count was above the quartile 3 (Q3) plus 3 times the interquartile range for this specific junction probe. The calculation of Q3 and interquartile range were done using the normalized data from the 96 retrospective samples. For the imbalance expression assay, a ratio of 5' P/3' P was calculated for *CREB3L1* and *CREB3L2* genes using the average normalized count values for the four 5' P and 3' P probes, respectively. In the case of *STAT6*, due to the high variability in the translocation breakpoint, 2 different ratios were calculated to uncover any exonic variant. Thus, a ratio was calculated for the diagnosis of SFT harboring those GF variants with an almost full length *STAT6* sequence (*STAT6 FULL*), and a ratio for SFT cases that only retained the transcriptional activator domain (TAD) of *STAT6* (*STAT6 TAD*). An imbalance threshold was set for each gene as the average negative-case exon imbalance ratio plus 5 times the standard deviation of all negative cases within the 96 retrospective samples. The codeset coverage and probe thresholds are detailed in Supplemental Tables 1 and 2. We verified that background values were similar when analyzing the whole series (172 samples). Thus, the positivity thresholds were almost identical and do not affect the identification of fusion transcripts in positive samples, nor do any false positives appear.

A 2-tailed Mann-Whitney test was used for the comparative statistical analysis of the average normalized counts across all *STAT6* exon probes between SFT and other sarcoma cases using GraphPad Prism v7 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, California).

RNA Quality Assessment

RNA quality control (QC) was based on the expression of 4 reference/housekeeping genes (actin beta [*ACTB*], glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase [*GAPDH*], succinate dehydrogenase complex flavoprotein subunit A [*SDHA*], and ubiquitin C [*UBC*]) included in the codeset. A sample was deemed "evaluable" if the normalized expression for all 4 control genes was greater than the 30% of the normalized expression average within the first 96 samples assessed. The normalized expression average

of reference genes and QC thresholds are detailed in Supplemental Table 3.

RESULTS

Retrospective Validation

We assayed 60 clinical retrospective samples with our first codeset version. Due to the lack of imbalance positivity for some SFT cases, we incorporated 4 junction probes to detect the most prevalent exonic variants of *NAB2::STAT6* fusions in a revised version of the codeset. This last codeset version was assessed by testing 36 additional samples. Almost all SFT samples were tested with both codeset versions, but only data from the second codeset are shown (Supplemental Table 4). Thus, in total, these codesets underwent validation using a cohort of 96 retrospective samples, comprising 82 tumor samples with confirmed GF expression and 14 samples with confirmed fusion-negative status upon previous targeted RNA-seq testing. Notably, the retrospective cohort encompasses 21 sarcoma subtypes, with a high representation of SFT and USRCS (Table 1; Supplemental Table 4).

Among the 96 retrospective cases, 6 did not meet the established RNA QC and were considered as nonevaluable. GF expression was demonstrated in 68 out of the 77 evaluable cases, displaying a concordant GF with targeted RNA-seq (sensitivity = 88.3%, 95% CI = .88082–.88312), thus exhibiting good performance across various sarcoma subtypes. No false positives were observed in this study (specificity = 100%).

However, the codeset encountered challenges in detecting capicua transcriptional repressor (CIC)-rearranged sarcomas, likely attributable to the considerable variability in the translocation breakpoints, in agreement with Chang et al.¹⁷ Likewise, while the codeset successfully identified 2 cases of epithelioid hemangioendothelioma (EHE) harboring the GF variants *WWTR1exon4::CAMTA1exon9* and *WWTR1exon3::CAMTA1exon9* (*WWTR1*, WW domain containing transcription regulator 1; *CAMTA1*, calmodulin binding transcription activator 1), it failed to detect 3 cases with the *WWTR1exon2::CAMTA1exon9* GF variant, which is not covered in the codeset. Regarding Ewing sarcoma (EwS) samples, 8 cases were examined (*EWSR1::FLI1*, $n = 2$; *EWSR1::ERG*, $n = 4$; *FUS::ERG*, $n = 2$; [*FLI1*, Fli-1 Proto-Oncogene, ETS Transcription Factor; *ERG*, ETS Transcription Factor *ERG*]). The codeset accurately identified 7 cases but failed to detect one EwS harboring the *EWSR1::ERG* GF. This might be due to the low expression of the GF as observed with targeted RNA-seq. The codeset also was unable to identify one pericytoma of bone (*ACTB::GLI1*; [*ACTB*, actin beta; *GLI1*, GLI family zinc finger 1]), and *MEAF6::PHF1*-rearranged sarcomas (*MEAF6*, MYST/Esa1 associated factor 6; *PHF1*, PHD finger protein 1).

The exon imbalance design facilitated the detection of GFs of SFTs which retain almost the complete sequence of *STAT6* gene (SFT *STAT6 FULL*), and GF involving *CREB3L1/2* in LGFMS/SEF cases. Indeed, a dual level of evidence was attained for diagnosing SFTs harboring one of the most prevalent GF variants, *NAB2ex4::STAT6ex2*, detected both with a junction probe and the imbalance assay (Figure, A and B). Intriguingly, not all SFTs that only retain the TAD of *STAT6* (SFTs in *STAT6 TAD* group) showed positive imbalanced ratios, although they were successfully identified by the junction design (Supplemental Figure 3). In addition, average

Table 1. Retrospective Case Summary

Histopathology	n	Targeted RNA-seq Gene Fusion (n)	NanoString				
			TP	FP	TN	FN	NE
Alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma	1	<i>PAX3::FOXO1</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
Angiomatoid fibrous histiocytoma	1	<i>EWSR1::CREB1</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
BCOR-rearranged sarcoma, <i>BCOR</i> IDT (USRCS)	4	<i>BCOR::CCNB3</i> (3); <i>BCOR</i> ITD (1)	3	0	0	0	1
CIC-rearranged sarcoma (USRCS)	3	<i>CIC::DUX4</i> (3)	1	0	0	1	1
Clear cell sarcoma	2	<i>EWSR1::ATF1</i> (2)	2	0	0	0	0
Congenital fibrosarcoma	1	<i>ETV6::NTRK3</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
Desmoplastic small round cell tumor	2	<i>EWSR1::WT1</i> (1)	2	0	0	0	0
Epithelioid hemangioendothelioma	6	<i>WWTR1::CAMTA1</i> (5); <i>YAP1::TFE3</i> (1)	3	0	0	3	0
Ewing sarcoma (USRCS)	8	<i>EWSR1::FLI1</i> (2); <i>EWSR1::ERG</i> (4); <i>FUS::ERG</i> (2)	7	0	0	1	0
Extraskeletal myxoid chondrosarcoma	3	<i>EWSR1::NR4A3</i> (2); <i>TAF15::NR4A3</i> (1)	2	0	0	0	1
High-grade endometrial stromal sarcoma	5	<i>ZC3H7B::BCOR</i> (3); <i>YWHAE::NUTM2B</i> (2)	5	0	0	0	0
Intracranial angiomatoid fibrous histiocytoma	1	<i>EWSR1::CREB1</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
Low-grade endometrial stromal sarcoma	4	<i>JAZF1::SUZ12</i> (2); <i>MEAF6::PHF1</i> (2)	2	0	0	1	1
Low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma/sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma	5	<i>EWSR1::CREB3L1</i> (1); <i>FUS::CREB3L2</i> (3); <i>FUS::CREM</i> (1)	4	0	0	0	1
Mesenchymal chondrosarcoma	2	<i>HEY1::NCOA2</i> (2)	2	0	0	0	0
Myxoid liposarcoma	2	<i>EWSR1::DDIT3</i> (1); <i>FUS::DDIT3</i> (1)	2	0	0	0	0
NFATc2-rearranged sarcomas (USRCS)	1	<i>EWSR1::NFATC2</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
Nodular fasciitis	1	<i>MYH9::USP6</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
NOS	1	<i>MEAF6::PHF1</i> (1)	0	0	0	1	0
Ossifying fibromyxoid tumor	1	<i>MEAF6::PHF1</i> (1)	0	0	0	1	0
Pericytoma of bone	1	<i>ACTB::GLI1</i> (1)	0	0	0	1	0
Primary pulmonary mixoid sarcoma	1	<i>EWSR1::CREB1</i> (1)	1	0	0	0	0
Solitary fibrous tumor	24	<i>NAB2::STAT6</i> (24)	24	0	0	0	0
Synovial sarcoma	2	<i>SS18::SSX2</i> (2)	2	0	0	0	0
Fusion-negative sarcomas	9	No fusion	0	0	8	0	1
Other rearranged mesenchymal tumors	3	<i>DLC1::PLAG1</i> (1); <i>RREB1::MKL2</i> (1), <i>MTAP::BRAF</i> (1)	0	0	3	0	0
Other tumors	2	NA	0	0	2	0	0
Total cases	96		68	0	13	9	6

Abbreviations: BCOR, BCL6 corepressor; BCOR ITD, BCOR internal tandem duplication; CIC, capicua transcriptional repressor; FN, false negative; FP, false positive; NA, not applicable; NE, non evaluable; NOS, not otherwise specified; RNA-seq, RNA sequencing; TN, true negative; TP, true positive; USRCS, undifferentiated small round cell sarcomas.

normalized counts across all *STAT6* exon probes were calculated in SFT (n = 24) and other sarcoma (n = 56) cases, revealing a statistically significant increased expression of *STAT6* in SFT versus other sarcomas (mean 12393 versus 2316, Mann-Whitney test, 2-tailed, *P* value < .001) (Figure, C). Significantly, *CREB3L1/2* exon imbalance was detectable in all LGFMS/SEF cases (Figure, D and E).

We also tested fusion-negative sarcomas (n = 9), other rearranged mesenchymal tumors (n = 3) that harbor GFs not covered by the NanoString panel, and other tumors non previously tested by targeted RNA-seq (n = 2). Thirteen out of 14 cases passed the RNA QC threshold, and all were negative for GF expression (specificity = 100%).

Prospective Clinical Evaluation

Additional assessment of the robustness of the codeset was conducted on a separate set of 76 samples collected prospectively, which were tested in parallel with FISH and/or targeted RNA-seq in the routine diagnostic workup. Forty-six out of 52 positive cases identified by FISH and/or targeted RNA-seq were detected using NanoString, with only 6 false-negative cases (sensitivity = 88.5%; 95% CI =

.88184–.88462) (Table 2 and Supplemental Table 5), demonstrating good performance in detecting pathognomonic GFs across various sarcoma subtypes. The imbalance design for identifying rearrangements of *STAT6*, *CREB3L1*, and *CREB3L2* genes proved to be highly efficient for diagnosing SFTs (*STAT6* FULL group) and LGFMS/SEF. Thus, the data corroborated observations from the validation cohort, with a double level of evidence for the diagnosis of SFTs with *NAB2exon4::STAT6exon2* GF variant, which were identified both by the exon imbalance and junction probe designs. SFT cases harboring the GF variants *NAB2exon6::STAT6exon6*, *NAB2exon6::STAT6exon17*, and *NAB2exon5::STAT6exon16* (*STAT6* TAD group) were successfully identified by the junction design. However, NanoString did not perform well in detecting 1 case each of CIC-rearranged sarcoma, clear cell sarcoma (CCS, *EWSR1exon10::ATF1exon2*, exonic variant not covered in the codeset; [*ATF1*, activating transcription factor 1]), clear cell sarcoma of the kidney (CCSK, *BCOR* ITD), EwS (*FUSexon10::ERGexon8*), low-grade endometrial stromal sarcoma (LGESS) with *PHF1* gene rearrangement (*JAZF1exon3::PHF1exon2*; [*JAZF1*, *JAZF* Zinc Finger 1]) and nodular fasciitis.

Fusion-negative sarcomas (n = 18) and other rearranged mesenchymal tumors not covered (n = 3) were also

Identification of solitary fibrous tumor (SFT) and low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma/sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma (LGFMS/SEF) entities by exon expression imbalance assay. (A) Normalized counts for the imbalance expression assays and the junction probes of a representative SFT with NAB2ex4::STAT6ex2 gene fusion. (B) Normalized counts of the junction probe for NAB2ex4::STAT6ex2 (Y axis) versus the expression imbalance ratios for STAT6 FULL gene fusion variants (X axis). (C) Average normalized counts of the probes targeting STAT6 in SFTs and other sarcomas in the retrospective cohort (****P value <.001). (D and E) Normalized counts of the imbalance expression assay of representative LGFMS/SEF cases with (D) CREB3L1 or (E) CREB3L2 gene rearrangements.

assessed (Supplemental Table 5). Seventeen out of 21 cases passed the RNA QC threshold; all were correctly identified as GF negative (specificity = 100%).

Diagnostic Yield

Next, we evaluated NanoString's diagnostic yield in comparison to FISH, the standard of care method used as the initial molecular diagnostic test for sarcomas in our setting. Seventy-three samples (prospective and retrospective) tested with all 3 methods (targeted RNA-seq, FISH, and NanoString) were compared, with targeted RNA-seq serving as the reference standard due to its higher analytic sensitivity. This cohort included 51 cases of GF-driven sarcomas, 18 fusion-negative cases, and 4 rearranged mesenchymal neoplasms not covered by the NanoString codeset (Table 3; Supplemental Table 6). We consider the result of the first FISH probing assay for diagnostic yield calculations, although subsequent FISH assays with additional probes were performed in several samples to reach a definitive diagnosis.

FISH and NanoString demonstrated good concordance in identifying GF of alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma, BCL6

corepressor (BCOR)-rearranged sarcomas, CCS, CCSK, desmoplastic small round cell tumor (DSRCT), nuclear factor of activated T cells 2 (NFATc2)-rearranged sarcomas, primary pulmonary myxoid sarcoma (PPMS), and synovial sarcomas (SS). However, certain sarcoma entities proved to be challenging for both technologies, including CIC-rearranged sarcomas, several EHE, and PHF1-rearranged sarcomas (Supplemental Table 6). The first FISH assay accurately identified 26 cases of GF-driven sarcomas, while NanoString successfully identified 40 cases out of 49 total evaluable cases. Consequently, the diagnostic yields of FISH and NanoString as a single initial assay were 53.1% and 81.6%, respectively. Notably, both techniques exhibited 100% specificity, indicating that no false-positive cases were detected. This significant increase in diagnostic yield observed with NanoString is mainly attributable to its multiplexing capability, eliminating the need for repeated FISH probing to achieve a conclusive result. In Supplemental Table 7 we list some cases to illustrate this, i.e., for cases 1, 2, and 3 (Supplemental Table 7), FISH resolved the differential diagnosis only after 2 or 3 different probes were tested. Case 1 was a lymph node infiltrated by a solid neoplasm of medium-large undifferentiated cells presenting

Table 2. Prospective Case Summary

Histopathology	NanoString ^a					
	n	TP	FP	TN	FN	NE
Alveolar rhabdomyosarcoma	6	5	0	0	0	1
Alveolar soft part sarcoma	1	1	0	0	0	0
CIC-rearranged sarcoma (USRCS)	2	0	0	0	1	1
Angiomatoid fibrous histiocytoma	1	1	0	0	0	0
Clear cell sarcoma	1	0	0	0	1	0
Clear cell sarcoma of the kidney (<i>BCOR</i> IDT) (USRCS)	2	1	0	0	1	0
Desmoplastic small round cell tumor	3	3	0	0	0	0
Ewing sarcoma (USRCS)	7	6	0	0	1	0
Extraskeletal myxoid chondrosarcoma	3	3	0	0	0	0
High-grade endometrial stromal sarcoma	2	2	0	0	0	0
Low-grade endometrial stromal sarcoma	3	2	0	0	1	0
Low-grade fibromyxoid sarcoma/sclerosing epithelioid fibrosarcoma	5	5	0	0	0	0
Mesenchymal chondrosarcoma	1	1	0	0	0	0
Myxoid liposarcoma	5	5	0	0	0	0
Nodular fasciitis	4	2	0	0	1	1
Solitary fibrous tumor	6	6	0	0	0	0
Synovial sarcoma	3	3	0	0	0	0
Other rearranged mesenchymal tumors	3	0	0	2	0	1
Fusion-negative sarcomas	18	0	0	15	0	3
Total cases	76	46	0	17	6	7

Abbreviations: *BCOR*, *BCL6* corepressor; *BCOR* ITD, *BCOR* internal tandem duplication; *CIC*, capicua transcriptional repressor; *FN*, false negative; *FP*, false positive; *NE*, non evaluable; *TN*, true negative; *TP*, true positive; *USRCS*, undifferentiated small round cell sarcomas.

^a Fluorescence in situ hybridization and/or RNA sequencing were considered as orthogonal standard of care techniques for comparison with NanoString determinations.

partial immunoexpression of cytokeratins. A broad initial differential diagnosis included carcinoma or sarcoma expressing epithelial markers. Sequential FISH assays with *SS18* (*SS18* subunit of *BAF* chromatin remodeling complex) and *TFE3* (transcription factor binding to *IGHM* enhancer 3) probes ruled out SS and alveolar soft part sarcoma (*ASPS*), respectively. Subsequent FISH testing with *ESWR1* probe was positive. A morphologic reevaluation of the case revealed a dense desmoplastic stroma in the tumor periphery, suggesting a desmoplastic small round cell tumor, which was confirmed with the identification of the GF of *ESWR1* and *WT1* transcription factor (*ESWR1::WT1*). Case 2 was a local relapse of a primary tumor diagnosed as *EwS*. However, the morphologic pattern was atypical and suggested other type of *USRCS*. Therefore, *CIC* rearrangement was tested but was negative, whereas *ESWR1* rearrangement was FISH positive, and finally targeted RNA-seq revealed the GF *ESWR1::NFATC2*, which could be detected with NanoString as well. Similarly, case 3, an intracranial mass, displayed immunohistochemical expression of *CD99* (*CD99* Molecule [Xg Blood Group]) and *NKX2.2* (*NK2* Homeobox 2), but showed atypical histomorphologic

and clinical presentation features, suggesting a *CIC*-rearranged sarcoma that could not be confirmed by FISH. A second FISH assay with *ESWR1* probe was positive in 14% of cells, which was confirmed with reflex testing (targeted RNA-seq). On the other hand, cases 4 to 7 in Supplemental Table 7 are representative of FISH pitfalls on detecting complex rearrangements that can be otherwise detected at RNA level. In case 4, FISH failed to detect *ESWR1* rearrangement, a common pitfall previously described, but both targeted RNA-seq and Nanostring identified the GF *ESWR1::ERG* in *EwS*.²⁶ In cases 5 and 6, with *SEF* and *LGFMS* suspected diagnosis, respectively, an *ESWR1* FISH probe was assayed with a negative result. This is possibly explained because of the complex/cryptic rearrangement generating *ESWR1::CREB3L1* fusion,^{27,28} which we were able to detect with NanoString using expression imbalance probes. Likewise, case 7 was assayed with *DDIT3* (*DNA* damage inducible transcript 3) and *NR4A3* (nuclear receptor subfamily 4 group A member 3) FISH probes for differential diagnosis between myxoid liposarcoma and extraskeletal myxoid chondrosarcoma, respectively, but both assays were negative. Targeted RNA-seq and NanoString detected the expression of *ESWR1ex7::DDIT3ex2*, evidencing that myxoid liposarcoma can exhibit cryptic *ESWR1::DDIT3* GF at the DNA level.²⁹

DISCUSSION

Here, we have validated and evaluated the clinical performance of a modified version of the sequence-specific probe set described by Chang et al¹⁷ that targets the RNA sequences at the junction site of 174 GF variants across 25 sarcoma types. This published version of the assay lacks

Table 3. Diagnostic Yield Analysis of NanoString and FISH-Based on Targeted RNA-seq as a Reference Technique

Targeted RNA-seq		FISH			NanoString			Total
P	N	P	N	NE	P	N	NE	
51	22	26	45	2	40	27	6	73

Abbreviations: *FISH*, fluorescence in situ hybridization; *N*, negative; *NE*, non evaluable; *P*, positive; *RNA-seq*, RNA sequencing.

coverage for some rare and newly described GF variants and GFs with highly variable fusion partners. Thus, we reconfigured this codeset to expand the diagnostic coverage and detect additional GFs using junction-spanning probes and expression imbalance probes.

The results of our study, utilizing both retrospective and prospective cohorts, revealed a high degree of sensitivity (>88%) and specificity (100%) of this NanoString panel compared with FISH and/or targeted RNA-seq. Our results are in agreement with those reported by Chang et al.¹⁷ This study comprised 212 cases (74 collected prospectively), 96 of which showed GF expression and demonstrated a sensitivity and specificity of 96% and 100%, respectively, compared to FISH and/or targeted RNA-seq. Later, a study by Song et al.²¹ assessed 106 soft tissue tumors derived from their archives, also using the codeset described by Chang et al.¹⁷ and reported a sensitivity and specificity of 85% and 100%, respectively, compared to the standard of care methods. Another study carried out by Haley et al.¹⁹ validated 4 different NanoString panels targeting hematologic, actionable, carcinoma, and sarcoma GFs. This last codeset is the same as that of Chang et al.¹⁷ and was validated in a small cohort of sarcoma samples comprising 25 retrospective cases with limited subtype heterogeneity, along with a prospective cohort with very low representation of mesenchymal malignancies (only 5 cases presented as pathognomonic sarcoma GF). The overall sensitivity and specificity in all 329 specimens (validation and consecutive clinical specimens of the 4 panels) tested in this study were 94.8% and 100%, respectively, compared with FISH/RT-PCR/next-generation sequencing assays. Sheth et al.²⁰ developed another study focused on validating this tool for identifying GF in sarcomas. They described the design of a customized codeset to detect 34 fusion transcripts associated with the most prevalent pediatric sarcomas and assayed it in 45 retrospective sarcoma samples from 38 patients. The results showed 100% concordance with the RT-PCR results. As most of the studies cited above dealt with retrospective cohorts, our work adds valuable evidence of good clinical performance in prospective clinical samples for implementation of the technology in the routine setting.

We observed superior diagnostic yield of NanoString versus FISH, with several cases illustrating that this was mainly due to the necessity for multiple and consecutive FISH testing in cases with uncertain differential diagnosis, and to the complexity of the rearrangement at DNA level (Supplemental Table 7). Moreover, NanoString provides valuable information about the partner of the GF, which is crucial for precise diagnosis in specific sarcoma subgroups such as USRCS, particularly those involving *EWSR1* gene rearrangements (see case 2 in Supplemental Table 7). Nevertheless, the codeset confronted challenges specifically in detecting CIC-rearranged sarcomas, EHE harboring some GF variants of *WWTR1::CAMTA1*, CCS with specific variants of *EWSR1::ATF1*, and *PHF1*-rearranged sarcomas due to high variability of the DNA breakpoint sequences involving many different exons. Including expression imbalance probes targeting these genes would be an ideal approach to optimize the codeset coverage. In this context, Goytain et al.¹⁸ have recently published an exon imbalance and gene expression assay that measures the expression of multiple exons across 23 genes involved in >25 sarcoma entities, targeting *ATF1*, *CAMTA*, *CREB3L1*, *CREB3L2*, and *PHF1* genes among others. Moreover, the identification of CIC-rearranged sarcomas is based on the detection of a CIC-associated

expression signature. Expression imbalance probes targeting *STAT6* gene were also included in their codeset, but *STAT6* expression imbalance was undetected in the 3 cases of SFTs assayed, and positive cases for *STAT6* rearrangement were just inferred by gene overexpression. This result is in agreement with our data: not all SFTs showed *STAT6* expression imbalance (especially those harboring *STAT6* TAD GF variants), but increased average counts across all *STAT6* exons was observed in SFTs (Figure, C). While morphology coupled with *STAT6* immunohistochemistry is typically sufficient for diagnosing SFT, specific cases, particularly those of dedifferentiated SFT, may not exhibit clear nuclear *STAT6* expression. Moreover, other mesenchymal neoplasms can also show nuclear *STAT6* expression, complicating the diagnostic process.³⁰ *NAB2::STAT6* GF arises upon a paracentric inversion on chromosome 12q13, where the 2 genes are adjacent, limiting FISH probing which lacks enough resolution for the detection of this alteration.³¹ Therefore, *NAB2::STAT6* junction-probes and *STAT6* imbalance probes were included in our codeset. In our cohorts, the SFT cases with *STAT6* TAD GF variants (*NAB2exon6::STAT6exon16*, *NAB2exon6::STAT6exon17*, and *NAB2exon5::STAT6exon16*) were successfully identified by the junction design included in the codeset. Thus, a dual level of evidence was achieved for diagnosing SFTs harboring the GF variant *NAB2exon4::STAT6exon2*, which were clearly identified by both the expression imbalance and junction designs. SFTs harboring these 4 GF variants represent more than 75% of the cases based on our experience.²⁵ Other SFT cases harboring less prevalent *NAB2::STAT6* GF variants were identified by the exon expression imbalance assay as well. Consequently, our codeset covers almost the total *NAB2::STAT6* GF variants reported and constitutes an invaluable test for molecular confirmation of SFT.

In conclusion, our study highlights the utility of NanoString technology as an efficient molecular first-line test for sarcoma diagnostics. Its multiplexing capacity greatly improves the diagnostic yield and therefore reduces the need for costly and time-consuming reflex testing such as targeted RNA-seq in many cases. In our setting, the turnaround time for the targeted RNA-seq assay is 5–7 working days, as it involves labor-intensive library preparation, library quantification, next-generation sequencing run, bioinformatics analysis with specific pipelines, and evaluation and interpretation of the results. With NanoString, the time is significantly reduced to 3–4 days, including RNA extraction, as it only requires an overnight hybridization of the probes and scanning the fluorescent reporters, with less hands-on time and a more streamlined interpretation of results. In terms of cost, the NanoString assay is approximately €300 per sample (when grouped in batches of 8–12), whereas the overall cost-per-specimen of targeted RNA-seq assay approximately doubles that of NanoString. Nanostring would be an affordable alternative in modest hospital centers, as the reagent costs equals other standard of care methods.^{17,18} Nevertheless, targeted RNA-seq would remain as a second-line diagnostic test, along with genome-wide assays (total RNA-seq or DNA methylation profiling) that are being increasingly adopted in clinics in recent years.¹⁴

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